

1 **Kinetic study of cell death decisions during trophectoderm commitment.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of a cell death program functioning in lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

8 Bax, Bok and Bcl6 were central effectors modulated most significantly. Other apoptotic effectors, like AEN and genes of the annexin family were affected. We also observed changes in caspase expression during execution of TE commitment. Casp3 was most closely associated with the TE differentiation program. Casp6 and Casp7 expression was also modulated during this specific phase of human embryonic development.

9
10
11
12 Citations

13 1. Janzen, V., Fleming, H.E., Riedt, T., Karlsson, G., Riese, M.J., Celso, C.L., Reynolds, G., Milne, C.D., Paige, C.J., Karlsson, S. and Woo, M., 2008. Hematopoietic stem cell responsiveness to exogenous signals is limited by caspase-3. Cell stem cell, 2(6), pp.584-594.

15 2. Fernando, P., Brunette, S. and Megeney, L.A., 2005. Neural stem cell differentiation is dependent upon endogenous caspase-3 activity. The FASEB journal, 19(12), pp.1671-1673.

17 3. Fujita, J., Crane, A.M., Souza, M.K., Dejosez, M., Kyba, M., Flavell, R.A., Thomson, J.A. and Zwaka, T.P., 2008. Caspase activity mediates the differentiation of embryonic stem cells. Cell stem cell, 2(6), pp.595-601.